

1.1 **Quality and pertinence of the project's research and innovation objectives (and the extent to which they are ambitious, and go beyond the state of the art)**

Resistive Plate Chambers (RPCs) are gaseous particle detectors with planar geometry and resistive electrodes. Their primary use in high energy physics (HEP) experiments is the trigger and identification of muons, thanks to their excellent timing (\sim ns) and spatial (\sim mm) resolution and their low cost (\sim 300 €/m² excluding readout electronics). This performance can only be achieved by employing the proper gas mixture, which currently contains more than 90% R134a (C₂H₂F₄), with the addition of Isobutane (i-C₄H₁₀) and Sulphur Hexafluoride (SF₆).

This mixture poses severe environmental issues: R134a and SF₆ are fluorinated greenhouse gasses (GHG) and The EU regulation 517/2014 imposed, in line with goal 13 of the United Nations Sustainable Development (*taking urgent actions to combat climate change and its impact*), a progressive phase-down in GHG production and usage, making the search for a more eco-friendly gas mixture for RPCs a necessity. As a first step, the use of the industrial substitute for R134a (tetrafluoropropene-1234ze, C₃H₂F₄ or HFO) is being studied. Several gas mixtures have been pointed out, and their performance is being studied and compared to the currently employed (R134a-based) one. Another aspect to be investigated is the long-term stability of detector performance, when operated with these new mixtures (aging studies). Indeed, a HEP experiment can operate for more than 20 years, and one must be sure that the chosen gas mixture can be used for this time without damaging the detectors.

Aging studies consist of exposing one or more detectors (powered on at nominal voltage) to a high-activity radioactive source, simulating the background conditions expected during nominal detector operation (with a higher intensity, to speed up the process) and study the evolution of their performance as a function of the accumulated dose. When ionizing particles traverse the detector, they interact with the gas, leading to the formation of pollutants (mainly ions, which depend on the gas mixture) inside the detector. These interact with its components, possibly causing physical damage and altering its performance (e.g. change in electrodes resistivity, increase of discharges and/or noise counting rate). These are known as *aging effects* and their comprehensive description requires the knowledge of the microscopical interactions between the pollutants and the detector components.

Aging studies have been carried out to validate the currently employed gas mixture and preliminary studies on HFO-based alternatives are ongoing. I am currently involved in the RPC ECOgas@GIF++ collaboration (**co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program** under GA n101004761), which is carrying out aging studies on several RPCs operated with HFO-based gas mixtures at the CERN Gamma Irradiation Facility (GIF++). Although these tests will provide critical information in the characterization of HFO-based gas mixtures, no microscopical modelization of the aging phenomena can be inferred. The main goal of this project is to decompose the aging phenomena observed in RPC detectors operated with HFO-based gas mixtures in its *building blocks* and to understand their origin. This will consist of three main objectives, briefly outlined here and described in details in Section 1.2:

- O1 (outgoing phase): compare chemical/electrical features of new and GIF++-aged RPC samples, related to WP2 (Section 3.1)
- O2 (outgoing phase): study RPC material compatibility with HFO and compare aging effects induced by a different source with respect to GIF++, related to WP2 (Section 3.1)
- O3 (return phase): develop a model to describe the observed phenomena and implement a computer simulation, related to WP3 (Section 3.1)

1.1 **Soundness of the proposed methodology (including interdisciplinary approaches, consideration of the gender dimension and other diversity aspects if relevant for the research project, and the quality of open science practices).**

The outgoing phase of the project is divided in **two parts**:

- 1) Systematic studies of the **chemical composition, electrical characteristics** (in terms of resistivity and conductivity), and **surface roughness** of new (unaged) and aged (following the GIF++ aging studies) RPC samples. This quantitatively measures the microscopical changes induced by the aging process. The hypothesis is that the impurities chemically interact with the RPC components, leading to microscopical composition modifications. Similar studies have been carried out for RPCs operated with R134a-based mixtures [1] but never with HFO-based ones. Moreover, the comparison of surface roughness in new and aged samples, would allow one to identify possible deposition of impurities on the detector surfaces (O1).
- 2) Analysis of the basic **components of the aging phenomena**. First, the compatibility of the materials used in RPC manufacture with HFO-based gas mixtures will be tested in a dedicated setup. Unaged RPC samples are exposed to an HFO-based mixture in an airtight vessel for a prolonged period of time (4-8 weeks) at a high temperature (~60°C) to increase chemical reactivity. No voltage will be applied to the samples and only the naturally-occurring chemical reactions will be involved. Following exposure, chemical and electrical analyses will be performed on the samples and compared to those of the GIF++-aged ones. If chemical reactions stimulated by simple exposure result in a similar degradation, this means that at least part of the aging is not related to the high currents induced in the detector by the radioactive source of GIF++. Secondly, unaged RPC samples will be placed in a similar vessel as the one used in the material compatibility studies and will be stressed with high currents induced by an artificial plasma source. This would simulate similar conditions to those of the GIF++ (with much higher currents), where interactions between the materials and ions/radicals take place. Following the exposure, the same chemical and electrical analyses will be performed on the samples and compared to those of the GIF++-aged ones. If similar effects are observed, this would imply that the source of irradiation does not play a significant role in the aging phenomena and also that the *rate of aging* (faster for the plasma source) does not lead to any substantial change. This studies would be carried out during a four-month secondment at the **Leibniz Institute for Plasma Science and Technology** (INP) in Greifswald, Germany (O2).

The new materials will be acquired from the companies responsible for the mass production of the RPCs installed at the LHC (*GT* and *Puricelli*). Samples of all the RPC building blocks will be bought: **eight Bakelite sheets** (50x50 cm² and 2 mm thick); two plane, two with graphite coating on one side (to uniformly distribute the high voltage) and no linseed oil (used to smooth out the bakelite surface) on the other, two the other way around (no graphite but linseed oil) and two with both linseed oil and graphite coating (as in an operating RPC). These are needed to study how each RPC component contributes to the final characteristics of the detector. Moreover, a 50 g sample of uncured linseed oil and 50 plastic spacers will be acquired. Together with these, I will provide the GIF++-aged RPC.

The chemical characterization of the detector components will be carried out by the CERN chemical analyses laboratory. I will maintain his current association with CERN (through the University of Torino) and will be able to profit from this service (free of charge). The chemical species abundance can be probed with an Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy, which provides a spectrum of the elemental composition in weight percentage. The comparison of the new and aged samples spectra will show what the products of the interaction between the gas mixture and the detector components are. Moreover, a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) can be used to perform morphological inspection of the new and aged samples, to visually observe the impurity depositions on the bakelite surfaces in different areas.

The electrical characterization of the samples will be carried out at ETH Zurich, with a dedicated setup to measure the electrical resistivity and permittivity of insulating materials. This consists of three measuring electrodes, in between which the sample to be analyzed is placed and an external voltage is applied. The apparatus measures the polarization-depolarization currents flowing in the materials and, using the ASTM D257-14 and IEC 62631-3-2 standards, it allows the computation of both the surface and bulk resistivity of the sample. Measurements on different locations will enable one to measure the uniformity of the resistivity and the comparison between the new and aged samples will reveal how the aging process affects the various detector components. Usually, the bulk resistivity of the whole detector is measured by filling the RPCs with pure argon gas. However, this does not provide local resistivity information, granted instead by the ETH setup.

Following the outgoing phase, I will return to the University of Torino, where he will perform a systematic data analysis campaign, aimed at formulating a model to explain the origin of the components deposited on the analyzed RPC samples (O3). Their formation is governed by the chemical reactions between the ions produced by the ionizing particles traversing the gas (whose nature will be provided by one of the PhD students currently working at ETH) and the charge carriers in bakelite and linseed oil. A model for charge conduction in these materials is provided by J. Va'Vra [2] and it can be used as a starting point. This assumes that the charge carriers in these materials are ions and it also hypothesizes their nature. At first, this can be considered and mechanisms to explain the creation of the observed impurities can be formulated. As a second step, profiting from the chemical analyses performed on new bakelite and linseed oil samples, a more realistic description of their chemical composition can be used in the model formulation. This will allow one to predict the expected aging effect if HFO gas is employed in place of $C_2H_2F_4$ in RPC detectors. This will also have implications in other sectors of particle detection (beside HEP), since RPCs are employed for cosmic rays detection over large areas (e.g. ANUBIS, Extreme Energy Event telescopes, ARGO and others).